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‘EFFECTS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN THE PRESENT WORLD’

* Mr. Shashank M. Hiremath

** Dr. Purushottam Bung

As it is widely said “Necessity is the mother of all inventions”, welcome to the 21st Century! Here we can find that there is need to dial a ten digit number to call someone (Speed dialing on mobile phones saves you your valuable time). Just one click and your mail travels across continents in few minutes rather than few weeks and you can turn your lights off without getting up from your chair. That’s right people; here in the 21st Century we have vastly advanced that crazy concept called technology. No more video cassettes, tape drives, floppy disks or tape recorders. No more wasting your money on music or movies. With just a click of a button you can have anything your restless mind wishes.

There are certain questions which need to be addressed before explaining the prospects and consequences of modern technology. What we have to ask ourselves now is, as technology advances, are we slowing down? Are we becoming victims of laziness and potential danger because of computers and cell phones? Are machines running or possibly ruining our lives? And so on. Here we present before our readers some prospects and consequences of modern technology:

Prospects: Technology has made living very comfortable and cozy. Electronic gadgets, cell phones, computers, even coffee vending machines are now so much more efficient, quick and easy to use for most people. Not to deny the fact that they are also lots of fun. We’ve got robots to vacuum our carpets and to scrub our floors. We have everything in our homes just a click of button away. It’s really amazing how quickly technology is developing and how far it has come. Had we ever thought that a single chip would replace an entire assembly line of workers? This has helped in eliminating human errors and made work faster and more efficient. There was a time when a person diagnosed as HIV positive was not accepted within the society as people thought that they would be infected too, even if they touched the infected person. But thanks to the advancements in the field of medicine science and health care, now these people are treated with love and care and have a hope to live. New researches about human anatomy are done every day. Doctors and researchers all over the world are working hard to introduce new medicines and treatments which can cure even the deadliest of diseases. This has surely added some years to the average life span of humans.

Consequences: When we watch any movie in any theatre, at the end of every movie it says “Don’t download the music, Buy it”. Even after reading such a message, we come back to our homes and download the film songs of our choice within minutes. We have all the songs we wanted. It’s not that we can’t afford a CD, but it is our laziness which gets first priority. Sometimes we get late to go to our offices. The reason is: we were trapped in a traffic jam. Why? Because someone was talking on the cell phone while driving and

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met with a brutal accident. Hacking is the most widespread and sophisticated crime nowadays. It has engulfed a major chunk of the young and talented pool of today. Every alternate day there is a new type of software virus, worms and trojans which we are made aware of. Modern inventions and techniques are not for everyone. It's only a rich man's dream to fly a personal jet with all the latest gadgets fitted in it. On microscopic level, technological advances are also widening the gap between the various classes of the society. There is a fear that this might cause unrest amongst the underprivileged or the less privileged section of the society and lead to more crimes and disparity. And how can we forget Hiroshima. Throughout most of the world, the name Hiroshima has come to represent man's technological capability for massive destruction. Hiroshima was the result of high-altitude bombing and long-range killing that came ever more to characterize World War II. Hiroshima opened the doors to a new world, a world in which it is possible for humanity to destroy itself by its own inventions of highly destructive ammunitions and weapons. Hiroshima was the world's first stare at a technology which could destroy countries, end civilization, and exclude a human future. What is unfortunate is that Hiroshima seems to be recreated every day with more and more scientists extravagant about their talents to improve weapons of mass destruction. Nuclear weapons do not distinguish people. They kill innocent men, women and children. The problem is if the disenchanted and disillusioned extremists of the world obtain nuclear weapons, they will use them to destroy everyone.

Perspectives on modern technology :

Today, we can't imagine ourselves without technological advancements such as airplanes, cars, microwaves, cell phones, computers, televisions and so on. However, technology doesn't stop here, but develops further. As technology develops, there are not only advantages, but disadvantages also from them. A few advantages of modern technology are that, one can save time and money and life will be made easier as a result of not having to do all the hard work. In contrast, the disadvantages of modern technology are that people may lose their jobs to machines that will do the work for them. In addition, machines and robots are too complex for most people to use.

We all would want a developed world with advanced technologies. But following are the reasons why we actually want a more advanced world with advanced technologies. Some major considerations are when you have advanced technologies, life is much easier as robots and machines would take over your daily life tasks. For example, daily life tasks might be serving your breakfast, cutting your lawn, or cleaning your room. With robots and machines doing one's responsibilities, one has time to relax. Another reason is because unlike humans, robots and machines do not make mistakes when programmed correctly. They always carry out tasks perfectly so you won't have to worry about making a mistake and receiving trouble.

Some other reasons why we want advanced technologies are because they save a great deal of time and money. For example, if you are a rich man who always had trouble employing talented employees, you can buy an industrial robot and use it for the rest of your life. Therefore, you won't have to use all your time employing talented people. Also, you will save a lot of money from not having to pay the employees. Another example of benefits from superior technology is that if there are new, developed vehicles that will transport people to anywhere speedily, so that one would not need to spend all those boring and restless

long hours in a usual transport vehicle to try to get to another place, which will save much time not only on long travels but also on daily commutes.

As there are numerous advantages from highly developed technology, there may be more number of disadvantages from them. One disadvantage is that as technology develops, robots and machines will take over many jobs and people may have to quit their jobs on contrast. As people quit their jobs, they will have hard time getting money which would make it hard for them to continue to meet day-to-day expenses. Moreover, as people invest less money in development of the economy, it would be difficult to monitor and control the economic development, especially if it is a country as large as the United States of America, the problem will influence the world greatly.

Another disadvantage of highly developed technology is that machines and robots are complex. It is hard to activate all the machines you have unless you can multitask. Think about it for a moment, if most people have trouble on computers and almost all of us don't know the actual understanding of computers abilities, how will we, the normal people, work with all the robots and machines? Moreover, just like computers, robots and machines will easily break and most of the time you won't know how to fix them and one will have to call someone to fix them. People will face problems over this and they will have to incur a big expense to repair them.

Even as there are as many advantages and disadvantages of technology, we personally wish a more advanced world with great technologies. It would be so cool to work out all the complicated machines and robots. Don't you think it will be awesome to press just a few complicated buttons than do the labor yourself? In the future it would be more about using your brain and being intelligent than doing the hard labor yourself. We hope these days to come within our lifetime.

Whether technology is a blessing or a curse?

Technology at work or home is both a blessing and a curse - subsequently to converse. Technology has enhanced performance at work with faster communication via email, video conferencing, chatting, the telephone etc. As teachers, we can upload grades that are available immediately for parents to view, to keep a track of students' performance, on situation testing and look up ideas for lesson plans by means of technology. The flip side of this issue are people who abuse their access to the technology on their job, such as constant instant messaging, emailing friends, and then the individuals who view inappropriate information on the web.

Transactions for millions and crores of rupees can be concluded with the stroke of a key using technology. Just about every job requires some form of technology to function - the supermarket, the movies, ordering job related items, etc. Our lives have been made easier due to technology. Employees sometimes have no privacy, for example, when we provide information about ourselves on the web it becomes a public knowledge. The information shared can be detrimental to a person's career if that information is of a personal nature.

Again, the flip side is that we can access information about situations and people at any time. For example, the property appraiser's office is mentioned in one site that is useful if one is buying or selling property. This is one way of assisting the public, and of course this data is useful for real estate developers to use.

Conclusion :

Technology has made a great impact on many individuals such as us in particular and the society as a whole. The positive ways that it affects society are many such as; it has brought lavishness to life, increases access to knowledge, provides a communication platform and has generally made life easier. On the other hand, it has made people lazy, overexposure can lead to internet addiction and it has made man excessively dependent on it.

These impacts have much changed the lives of individuals as well. The arguments against its benefits are many. Once, human life used to be restricted because no technological applications were available. Daily routine life then involved a lot of physical activity but now in modern times, people have more luxury and in the process have neglected the need for activity and exercise. Though technology may be advantageous in some ways, people dispute that it is not been that beneficial because it has sprouted many unethical practices such as hacking, computer espionage, addiction and lack of regulation. It has also deprived man of the warmth of being in contact with the others. Communication has lost its personal touch. People have also become overly dependent on machines and technology to do their work for them. They rely on machines than human intellect. Machines replacing human beings may cause great issues such as unemployment and crime. With the developments in technology, we may be able to enjoy all the pricey luxuries but miss out on the tiny priceless joys of life.

For the prospects of technology, the use of advanced technologies like robotics and artificial intelligence has proved helpful in life-risking tasks like mining and space exploration. The Internet has brought an important positive change to the entertainment and advertising industry. Advertisements can reach the masses within seconds over the Internet. The entertainment media has progressed only because of the advancements in technology. Mobile phones have broadened the horizons of communication by enabling convenient long-distance. End of the day people must not forget a fact that technology has enabled man to reach the moon and study its surroundings, whereas he doesn't know who his neighbours are. Not sure where we are all headed with this but it's going to be immeasurably different than what we can expect in times to come.

